

Legal Analysis of Formation of Socio-Economic Development of the Region on the Basis of "Green" Economy

Shomirzaev Abdugaffor Abdujabbor ugli

Doctoral student of Termez state university, Faculty of economics and tourism, Digital economy, business management and econometrics department

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 July 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Aug 2024; **Published:** 04 Sep 2024

Abstract: In this article, legal analysis of transformation to the "green" economy, and target indicators of transition to "green economy" in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 were described.

Keywords: "green" growth, sustainable development, target indicators, legal analysis.

The concept of "green" economy is usually recognized as an alternative word to sustainable development however, "green" economy does not directly mean sustainable development, it is the way to achieve sustainable development. The "green" economy is defined as an economic system that aims to achieve sustainable development without degrading the environment. It focuses on several sectors, such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, innovation and water management. Legal frameworks play an essential role in shaping policies that support this type of economy. National law supports protecting environment, efficient resource use and investing in green technologies. For some examples of the laws, regulating emissions, waste management and conservation effort. In Uzbekistan, also, government body announced environmental laws to promote green economics. According to 51st goal of the strategy of "Uzbekistan - 2030", Uzbekistan aims to accelerate the transition of "green" economy and increase to use renewable energy until 2030. Also, the goal includes:

- To increase the share of renewable energy sources to 25 thousand MW and to 40% of the total consumption;
- Development of the market of "green certificates" and introduction of the practice of "ecological marking" in the industry;
- Reducing natural gas consumption by upgrading 3 thermal power plants with a capacity of 3 GW;
- introduction of energy efficiency assessment system (energo-audit) of apartments in high-rise buildings;
- Switching public transport to environmentally friendly fuel in cities;
- Creation of a monitoring system (MRV) covering all greenhouse gases in the field of climate change;
- A 30 percent reduction in greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP from 2010 levels.

Furthermore, according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2022, "ON MEASURES TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE REFORMS FOR THE TRANSITION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO A "GREEN" ECONOMY BY 2030" Uzbekistan government aims to promote consumption of renewable energy, efficient usage of natural resources and minimize emission of greenhouse gases. As a part of the laws, "the program of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030" was announced. Goals of the program include:

- to accelerate the transition to a "green" economy;
- to support for "green" investment;
- technological modernization and introduction of "green" technologies.

The program includes 6 priority directions¹:

- sustainable and efficient use of natural resources;
- strengthening the stability of the national economy against natural disasters and climate change;
- national economy, specifically ensuring the 'green' and low-carbon development of the industry;
- introducing innovations and attracting effective "green" investments;
- development of sustainable and inclusive "green" urbanization;
- Support the population and their habitats that may be greatly affected during the transition to a "green" economy;

Also, these priority directions have several sub-sections and main tasks. (for more information please visit this official site <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-6303230>)

Target indicator of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030²

1st table

№	Indicators	Unit of measure	2022	2024	2026	2028	2030
1.	Reduction of energy consumption per unit of GDP (compared to 2021)	%	5,0	14,0	22,0	27,0	30,0
2.	Electricity consumption in industry, its share in total consumption	%	26,0	25,0	23,0	21,0	20,0
3.	Increasing the share of renewable energy sources in the total volume of electricity production (along with hydropower)	%	8,0	9,0	24,3	29,0	30,5
		kW/h	6,5	8,6	25,0	34,0	40,7
4.	Construction of small power solar photoelectric plants	MW	10,0	150,0	400,0	800,0	1500,0
5.	Population with access to improved drinking water sources, relative to the total population	%	69,7	80,93	87,12	88,5	90,0
6.	Increasing tree and shrub stocks in the forest fund territories	million m ³	64,2	68,1	77,0	85,5	92,3
7.	Expansion of green spaces in cities within the framework of the "Green Space" project (relative to the total area of the settlement)	%	8,3	12,4	15,8	23,8	30,0
8.	Level of processing of generated solid household waste	%	30,0	40,0	50,0	60,0	65,0

¹ <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-6303230>

² <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/>

In general, the table above refers target indicators of transformation of “green economy” in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. According to the table above, the following goals have been set to be achieved, such as more efficient use of energy, promoting renewable energy production like solar power, hydropower, increasing green spaces, reforestation and so on.

References.

1. www.lex.uz "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy. Presidential Decree No. 158.
2. www.lex.uz Presidential Decree No. 436 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030".
3. www.lex.uz National database of legislative information of the Republic of Uzbekistan.